

AN ONBOARD SPACECRAFT RENDEZVOUS GUIDANCE APPROACH LEVERAGING A MONOMIAL METHOD

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This paper applies a recently developed optimization technique called a *monomial method* to the spacecraft station-keeping and rendezvous guidance problem. The methodology involves pre-computing nonlinear expansions that, when paired with stationary coordinates on a manifold, form an approximate basis for describing functions of interest, such as the spacecraft state, equality/inequality constraints, and cost functions. By this approach, an optimal multi-maneuver guidance procedure then simplifies to finding the optimal placement of the stationary coordinates on a product manifold – a problem which can be solved quickly using sequential convex optimization, implemented using CVXPY.

INTRODUCTION

In the traditional spaceflight guidance and control paradigm, rendezvous and station-keeping trajectories are computed by careful “on-ground” planning by teams of engineers who jointly consider all relevant constraints and the expected dispersions to be encountered upon execution.¹ The reference guidance solution is then followed by a simple closed-loop control policy onboard. Upcoming spaceflight architectures and capabilities foresee spacecraft rendezvous becoming a routine, even daily occurrence, and at times executing over much faster timescales and/or much farther from Earth than the historical norms. For this to be practical, there is a need for automating spacecraft rendezvous from long-range to terminal close-proximity procedures under a unified, reliable, and efficient guidance formulation. This involves developing fuel- or time-efficient trajectories subject to the nonlinear dynamics, the expected dispersions, and a variety of nonlinear state constraints. In spacecraft onboard guidance, in lieu of correcting the executed trajectory to a pre-computed guidance solution, a new optimal guidance solution is computed whenever the guidance scheme is called (see e.g. Reference 2 for a discussion of such onboard closed-loop guidance in deep space applications).

Recent works have explored the spacecraft rendezvous and station-keeping problem using sequential convex programming (e.g. Refs. 3, 4) which is gaining popularity in the spaceflight guidance community. In this work, we apply a newly developed optimization technique called the *monomial method*⁵ to demonstrate its potential use in spacecraft rendezvous and station-keeping guidance. This approach relies on differential algebra (DA),⁶ organization and manipulation of sequences and matrices of monomials, and sequential convex programming⁷ on a novel problem

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manifold. By this methodology, an originally challenging nonlinear optimal guidance problem can be posed in a format that is rapidly solvable onboard. In this early work, we preview a deterministic guidance application which can be applied rapidly and repeatedly in a dispersed setting, facilitating closed-loop guidance. We explore both the case of Keplerian and cislunar circular 3-body dynamics (Earth–Moon–Spacecraft) as captured by the circular restricted three-body problem (CR3BP), but the methodology could equivalently be applied in any explicit dynamical model without modification. This work previews early results from an ongoing effort to develop spacecraft guidance schemes using a monomial method.

METHODOLOGY

Spacecraft Rendezvous and Station-Keeping

The dynamics under consideration are those of relative motion in the vicinity of a target orbit. Two orbital rendezvous/station-keeping scenarios are considered in this work: low-Earth orbit (LEO) and cislunar space. For the former, we provide details on the long-range (e.g. nonlinear) dynamics in the vicinity of a circular Keplerian orbit. This problem is parameterized by the nonlinear equations below for local vertical-local horizontal (LVLH) relative position $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)^\top$ and velocity $\mathbf{v} = (\dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z})$:⁸

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} - xn^2 - \frac{\mu}{R^2} = -\frac{\mu}{r^3}(R+x) \quad (1a)$$

$$\ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} - yn^2 = -\frac{\mu}{r^3}y \quad (1b)$$

$$\ddot{z} = -\frac{\mu}{r^3}z \quad (1c)$$

where R is the circular target orbit radius, n is its orbital mean motion, $r = \sqrt{(R+x)^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ is the chaser’s instantaneous orbit radius, and velocities are measured with respect to the target-centered LVLH frame. The task of rendezvous is to drive the relative state to $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}$ (or rather, specifically the coordinates of the docking port) with $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$, in a safe and robust manner. This is often achieved jointly with safety constraints such as range-based passive drift safety⁴ or terminal approach cone constraints. Relaxing such constraints in the case of a “virtual target”, the problem reduces to basic station-keeping on a prescribed orbit, regulating to the LVLH origin. Note an analog to the Keplerian equations of Eq. (1) exist for the circular restricted three-body problem (CR3BP) in the cislunar case, applying the relevant LVLH transport equations to the relative dynamics – see Reference 9. Nevertheless, for the preliminary results of cislunar rendezvous, the work presented in this paper adopts a nonlinear relative equation of motion in the relative synodic frame under the assumption that both the target and the chaser are subject to CR3BP dynamics. The non-dimensional relative equations of motion are expressed as:

$$\ddot{x} = 2\dot{y} + x + (1-\mu) \left[\frac{\mu + x_t}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1t}\|^3} - \frac{\mu + x_t + x}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1t} + \boldsymbol{\rho}\|^3} \right] + \mu \left[\frac{\mu + x_t - 1}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2t}\|^3} - \frac{\mu + x_t + x - 1}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2t} + \boldsymbol{\rho}\|^3} \right] \quad (2a)$$

$$\ddot{y} = -2\dot{x} + y + (1-\mu) \left[\frac{y_t}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1t}\|^3} - \frac{y_t + y}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1t} + \boldsymbol{\rho}\|^3} \right] + \mu \left[\frac{y_t}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2t}\|^3} - \frac{y_t + y}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2t} + \boldsymbol{\rho}\|^3} \right] \quad (2b)$$

$$\ddot{z} = (1-\mu) \left[\frac{z_t}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1t}\|^3} - \frac{z_t + z}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1t} + \boldsymbol{\rho}\|^3} \right] + \mu \left[\frac{z_t}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2t}\|^3} - \frac{z_t + z}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2t} + \boldsymbol{\rho}\|^3} \right] \quad (2c)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ represents the chaser’s relative position with respect to the target, while \mathbf{r}_{1t} and \mathbf{r}_{2t} denote the target’s position relative to the Earth and the Moon, respectively.

Trajectory Optimization Using the Monomial Method

The foundation of this work is an optimization technique called the *monomial method*, first formalized in Reference 5. The method involves pre-computing truncated Taylor expansions of dynamics and equality/inequality constraint functions of interest leveraging differential algebra (DA). Then, noting the inherent relationship between the monomials in the multivariate Taylor expansions, this technique approximates the problem's nonlinear functions in Euclidean space as linear functions on a manifold of analytic structure. Optimization problems can then be solved with high speed and stability on this manifold in a direct manner. The method affords the user significant computational savings in any context requiring the repeated solution of similar optimization problems in which the expansions and the space can be reused. The spacecraft station-keeping and rendezvous guidance problems are ideal for this formulation when the necessary expansions can be pre-computed and stored onboard for a given reference trajectory. This work features some results from Reference 10 but also adds results from a cislunar rendezvous example, and explores some simple arguments for implementing a simple monomial method-based guidance scheme.

In this work we explore guidance policies computing an optimal solution to general nonlinear problems of the following form for a spacecraft translational state $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{r}^\top, \mathbf{v}^\top)^\top$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{\Delta \mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \Delta \mathbf{v}_K} \quad & J = \sum_{i=1}^K \|\Delta \mathbf{v}_i\| \\
 \text{subject to} \quad & \mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{x}_0 \\
 & \mathbf{x}(t_f) = \mathbf{x}_{\text{goal}} \\
 & \mathbf{r}(t_{b_i}^+) = \mathbf{r}(t_{b_i}^-) \\
 & \mathbf{v}(t_{b_i}^+) = \mathbf{v}(t_{b_i}^-) + \Delta \mathbf{v}_i \\
 & \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) = \mathbf{0} \\
 & \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \leq \mathbf{0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where the first two constraints are boundary conditions, the second two are kinematic requirements of the impulsive maneuver assumption, and the final two are nonlinear equality and inequality constraints that can be nonlinear but must be smooth and smoothly differentiable with respect to the relative state \mathbf{x} . This problem is converted into the monomial formulation as Eq. (4):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{\mathbf{c}_j(t_i) \forall i \in [1, K]} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^K \|\Psi_{v,j}(t_i) (\mathbf{c}_j(t_i) - \mathbf{c}_j(t_{i-1}))\| \\
 \text{subject to} \quad & \mathbf{c}_j(t_0) = \mathbf{c}_{j,0} \\
 & \mathbf{c}_j(t_K) = \mathbf{c}_{j,\text{goal}} \\
 & \mathbf{c}_j(t_i) - \mathbf{c}_j(t_{i-1}) \in \ker(\Psi_{r,j}(t_i)) \\
 & \Gamma_{g,i} \mathbf{c}_j(t_i) = \mathbf{b}_{g,i} \quad \forall i \\
 & \Gamma_{h,i} \mathbf{c}_j(t_i) \leq \mathbf{b}_{h,i} \quad \forall i \\
 & \mathbf{c}_j(t_i) \in \mathcal{C}^{(N,j)}, \quad \forall i \geq 1
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where $\mathbf{c}_j(t_i)$ is a single monomial state vector node, $t_K = t_f$ for a fixed-time formulation, $\Psi_j(t_i)$ is a two-dimensional representation of the coefficients in an order- j Taylor series expansion, equivalent to the information contained in the more familiar state transition tensor mapping from t_0 to t_i . The Ψ_r denotes the first three (position-associated) rows and Ψ_v denotes the latter three (velocity-associated) rows. Unlike the state transition tensor, this matrix is two-dimensional, with

each column containing the evaluation of the fundamental solution $\psi_\beta(t)$ corresponding to a unique monomial, evaluated at time t_i :

$$\psi_\beta(t) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{c}_j[\beta]} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{c}_j[\beta]$ is the unique scalar monomial term from position β of the vector monomial sequence \mathbf{c}_j , which contains terms up to order j . In this work, the monomial coordinates $\mathbf{c}_j(t_i)$ are node points which yield a transcription scheme defined by an *osculating relationship*:¹⁰

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \Psi_j(t)\mathbf{c}_j(t_i) \text{ for } t_i \leq t < t_{i+1} \quad (6)$$

where in this case $\mathbf{c}_j(t_i)$ is built from the fictitious initial conditions at time t_0 that would, by the flow of the natural dynamics, yield $\mathbf{x}(t)$ for $t_i \leq t < t_{i+1}$, or from time t_i until the next maneuver. This feature is not a core concept from the monomial method, but is rather a method of reusing the same sequence of flattened STTs to parameterize the entire trajectory, avoiding entirely the need for map inversions and products (or equivalently, “chaining” of the STTs). This is primarily intended to simplify analysis for characterizing validity and accuracy of the guidance solution. At the times t_i for $1 \leq i \leq K$, we allow for the possibility of maneuvers but require the positions to match before and after the instantaneous burn. This explains the first and fourth expressions in Eq. (4), respectively. The matrices $\Gamma_{g,i}$ and $\Gamma_{h,i}$ each provide a linear map from $\mathbf{c}_j(t_i)$ to the associated nonlinear constraint.

Eq. (4) is otherwise convex in the $\mathbf{c}_j(t_i)$ except for the last expression, which constrains the monomial states to a smooth manifold. This problem is solved using the same monomial-based SCP scheme discussed in Reference 5, by which the dimensionality of free variables is reduced back down to NK variables from $K_j K$ variables, where $N = 6$ and K_j is the total number of unique monomials that can be constructed up to order j from an N -dimensional set of independent variables. Within each iteration of the SCP, changes to any given nonlinear function $\Gamma_{(\cdot)}\mathbf{c}_j$ are approximated in the tangent space of the monomial manifold, noting that the monomial Jacobian $\partial \mathbf{c}_j / \partial \mathbf{c}_1$ is just a linear function of \mathbf{c}_j :

$$\Gamma_{(\cdot)}\left(\mathbf{c}_j^\dagger + \delta \mathbf{c}_j\right) \approx \Gamma_{(\cdot)}\left(\mathbf{c}_j^\dagger + \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}_j}{\partial \mathbf{c}_1} \delta \mathbf{c}_1\right) \quad (7)$$

This holds within some region of validity $\|\delta \mathbf{c}_1\| < d$. Between calls to the convex solver, the only nonlinear computation is a retraction operation, updating the new reference point \mathbf{c}_j^\dagger . As a result, the computational time for numerical operations between CVXPY calls are negligible. There is another potential advantage: evaluating the effect of small deviations in decision variables on all cost and constraint functions is numerically inexpensive, requiring only sampling on the manifold. As a result, sampling can be used to augment the SCP for particularly challenging functions, or incorporated into a stochastic approach.

Figure 1 depicts how the impulsive maneuver trajectory optimization problem for translational spacecraft state $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is transcribed as a path-planning problem on the N -dimensional monomial manifold $\mathcal{C}^{(N,j)}$, whereby the i^{th} impulsive maneuver at time t_{b_i} manifests as a jump on the discretized path. Via the formalisms of Reference 5, this problem can also be posed as the optimization of a single state on a higher-dimensional *product manifold*, but for our purposes this illustration is more approachable.

Figure 1: Impulsive Maneuver Trajectory Optimization as Path-Planning on Monomial Manifold

Computationally Efficient Guidance Methodology

The basic idea of the application of a closed-loop guidance policy is illustrated in Figure 2. A guidance problem \mathcal{Q} is defined based on the template of Eq. (3) (e.g. specifying K candidate maneuver times, the start and end times, the goal state, and the constraint functions \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{h}). Application of differential algebra establishes the monomial formulation of the guidance problem $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}$, using a process discussed in Reference 5, which is to be reused every time guidance needs to be called. This formulation contains DA-based expansions Γ_g and Γ_h of the constraints, and contains the custom Python functions necessary to operate on the monomial manifold $\mathcal{C}^{(N,j)}$. For a trajectory originally parameterized on some fixed-time interval $\mathcal{T} = [t_0, t_f]$, as the trajectory is followed over time, the new “initial time” $\hat{t}_0 \in \mathcal{T}$ for the onboard guidance problem progresses from t_0 to t_f . Likewise the input “initial” state for the guidance problem, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$ is the best estimate of the spacecraft state at time \hat{t}_0 .

Figure 2: Fast Closed-Loop Rendezvous Guidance Approach

Optimization of the resulting problem on the monomial manifold is done via a sequential convex programming (SCP) approach taking place on the monomial manifold, prototyped in Python using CVXPY.^{11,12} The fact that $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}$ is defined only once means that we also have the option to use CVXPYgen¹³ to create a custom pre-compiled solver implementation in C++, reusing the prob-

lem definition and parsing details to save computation time in each step of the SCP. Obtaining a disciplined parameterized programming (DPP) for our SCP approach requires that all problem expressions be affine in problem parameters. This can be done by introducing auxiliary variables and extra constraints for the case of the non-affine conditions of the form of Eq. (7). This adds to the total number of constraints for CVXPY to solve, which offsets somewhat the computational savings of having a pre-compiled solver.

For the guidance problem defined by Eq. (4), note that information and variables (e.g. trajectory nodes) from times *in the past*, $\tau < \hat{t}_0$, become irrelevant to the closed-loop guidance task on the new interval $[\hat{t}_0, t_f]$. This can be accommodated either by removing free variables associated with trajectory nodes $t_i < \hat{t}_0$ and their associated tensor expansions $\Psi_j(t_i)$, $\Gamma_{g,i}$ and $\Gamma_{h,i}$, or by activating constraints on those nodes such that they equal their executed historical value, effectively removing them from the current guidance problem while preserving the overall structure/dimensionality of the problem, so that a pre-compiled solver can still be used. This will be explored in future work, and for now we simply demonstrate the computation of a single guidance solution for each case.

Constraints

A modern spacecraft rendezvous guidance scheme must accommodate a variety of possible constraints mainly based on practical drivers of rendezvous such as safety, efficiency, and executability. This could include free-drift (also called *passive safety*) constraints, in which it is required that the trajectory after a missed maneuver of the chaser spacecraft will not come closer than a certain minimum range of the target. It could also include a waypoint-based/range-regulating schedule, approach cone constraints limiting the direction with which a chaser spacecraft can approach the target, and thruster timing/magnitude and plume impingement constraints. See References 4, 14 and references therein for more discussion of spacecraft rendezvous constraints.

Monomial methods are quite flexible in terms of the types of constraints they admit, with the only strict mathematical requirement being that the constraint function should be smooth, smoothly differentiable, and should admit a locally convergent Taylor series expansion. Note however that to be certain to avoid the solver getting “stuck” in the sequential solution process on the manifold, some constraint functions might require a more advanced approach than the simple method of SCP operating in the tangent bundle of $\mathcal{C}^{(N,j)}$ which we have used so far. In this work we demonstrate rendezvous guidance with two different types of constraints which have worked well. The first is a nonlinear range constraint, reproduced below for Cartesian and spherical working coordinates:

$$\varrho(t_i) = \sqrt{\delta r^2 + 2r\delta r + 2r^2 - 2r(r + \delta r)\cos\delta\phi\cos\delta\theta} \geq \varrho_{\min}(t_i) \quad (8a)$$

$$\varrho(t_i) = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \geq \varrho_{\min}(t_i) \quad (8b)$$

where the min range constraint is applied at each discretization node. Different range constraints can be applied at different times, producing a range schedule:

$$\varrho_{\min} = \begin{cases} \rho_1 & t \leq T_1 \\ \rho_2 & T_1 < t \leq T_2 \\ \rho_3 & T_2 < t \leq T_3 \\ \dots & \dots \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Enforcing the free-drift constraint for times $t > t_i$ can also be achieved by similar equations. We also explore terminal cone constraints with half-angle γ and unit vector \mathbf{n} which points along the

docking axis of the target spacecraft, with \mathbf{r}_f denoting a final target position, as depicted in Fig. 3.

$$\|\mathbf{r}(t_i) - \mathbf{r}_f\| \cos \gamma \leq \mathbf{n}^\top (\mathbf{r}(t_i) - \mathbf{r}_f) \quad (10)$$

Taylor expansion of inequality constraints such as Eqs. (8) and Eq. (10) yields constraints affine in

Figure 3: Approach Cone Constraint for Spacecraft Rendezvous

the monomial state vector in the same form as shown in Eq. (4).

RESULTS

LEO Rendezvous Guidance

We first provide some simple rendezvous trajectories computed by applying the monomial method to long-range spacecraft rendezvous in the vicinity of a circular Keplerian orbit. These trajectories are based on recent work by the authors.¹⁰ Relevant problem parameters are provided in Table 1. Figure 4 provides an optimized open-loop trajectory computed using our SCP approach, shown in purple, with the optimal maneuver times approximated by those obtained from a linearization-based initial guess (i.e. Eq. (4) truncated to the linear case $j = 1$), and the maneuvers are then refined via SCP on the monomial manifold for order j . The compute time for this trajectory is 0.296s in Python, solved in 3 iterations using CVXPY and our custom functions for computing and manipulating monomials. The total delta-V for this long-range rendezvous example is 226.31 m/s. Also depicted is the open-loop execution of the linearized guidance solution, in orange, which fails to achieve the goal due to insufficiently capturing the nonlinear dynamics prevalent at a range of thousands of km.

Figure 4: Optimal Rendezvous with Maneuver Times Fixed

Figure 5 solves the same problem but with many candidate maneuver times (to give an approximation of the truly optimal solution with maneuver times free), and obtains a policy with an improved

Table 1: LEO Rendezvous Guidance Examples

Category	Values
SCP parameters	
Trust region	Fixed, $d = 0.1$
Slack penalty weight	$w = 10^3$
Method	ECOS
Convergence condition	Free var. update norm $< 10^{-7}$
SCP (fixed burn times)	
Burn indices	[0, 40, 83, 116]
Δv	226.31 m/s
Runtime	0.296s
Open-loop end error (pos/vel norm), $j = 4$	0.038 km, 0.193 m/s
No. iterations needed	6
SCP (free burn times)	
Burn indices	[0, 44, 81, 117]
Δv	222.22 m/s
Runtime	3.89s
Open-loop end error (pos/vel norm), $j = 4$	0.0857 km, 0.332 m/s
No. iterations needed	10
SCP (constrained)	
Δv	239.66 m/s
Runtime	5.86s
Open-loop end error (pos/vel norm), $j = 4$	0.092 km, 0.155 m/s

delta-V of 222.22 m/s, but at a larger computational cost, with a runtime of 3.89s due to more than tenfold expansion of the number of trajectory nodes, and hence also free variables.

Figure 5: Optimal Rendezvous with Many Maneuver Time Options

Figure 6 shows the range vs. time for the original unconstrained problem (orange) vs. a constrained policy (blue) computed to satisfy range schedule constraints, depicted with the dashed black lines. The result is a satisfactory policy with a new delta-V of 239.66 m/s, with the introduction of new burn times by the optimizer to satisfy the constraints.

Figure 6: Range vs. Time, Constrained and Unconstrained

NRHO Rendezvous Guidance

This section presents the results of the aforementioned guidance method applied to rendezvous in the cislunar domain, thus with CR3BP differential dynamics in the vicinity of an NRHO as the dynamical model used to pre-compute $\Psi_j(t)$ for all $t \in [t_0, t_f]$. Relevant problem parameters are provided in Table 2. Figure 7 shows the optimal trajectory and the location of the maneuvers for rendezvous scenario with an initial separation of approximately 50 km. This trajectory is subjected to a minimum inter-range separation in the initial phase and an approach cone in the final phase. Note that because the timescale of this rendezvous problem is low in comparison to the NRHO orbit period, the characteristic motion between maneuvers is quasi-rectilinear. At this scale it is hard to see that the final approach takes place within the approach cone. The solution consists of 6 impulsive maneuvers with a delta-V of 7.577 m/s. The SCP algorithm converges in 15 iterations in 12.165 s. Finally, Figure 8 shows the step-function minimum range and inter-spacecraft range over time, and a zoomed-in view of the final trajectory nodes, highlighting the presence of the trajectory inside the approach cone.

Table 2: NRHO Rendezvous Example

Control Interval	TOF = 1.6312 days, discretized into 100 points
Linear Guidance	
Burn info	Burn indices: [1, 74], $\Delta v = 7.57587$ m/s
Performance	Runtime: 0.9251s, Open-loop range error: > 10 km
SCP-based guidance	
Burn info	Burn indices: [1, 16, 20, 21, 80, 99], $\Delta v = 7.5766$ m/s
Performance	Runtime: 12.165s (15 iter.), Open-loop error: $\sim 10^{-2}$ km, $\sim 10^{-4}$ m/s

CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates an early application of a monomial method for localized nonlinear optimization to solving constrained trajectory optimization problems for the purpose of onboard guidance for spacecraft rendezvous and station-keeping. Constrained rendezvous problems in LEO and NRHO are solved under the assumption of impulsive maneuvers. In this approach, all of the nonlinear information needed to capture the motion of trajectories in the vicinity of a target spacecraft or operating orbit are computed in advance using a differential algebra-driven approach. This information is equivalent to having the state transition tensor (STT) pre-computed at various times of

Figure 7: Optimal relative trajectory in the relative synodic frame with short initial separation and state constraints (approach cone and minimum-range)

Figure 8: State constraints in nonlinear convex rendezvous guidance.

interest. The strength of this approach is in its potential for computational efficiency and robustness, and the fact that it can be applied in any dynamical environment. A weakness is that it requires storing the necessary pre-computed expansions, and these expansions must be re-computed if the operating/target orbit changes significantly. Opportunities for future work are extensive, including exploring updated solution strategy for optimizing on the monomial manifold, more physically realistic scenarios and constraints, exploration of stochasticity, and guarantees of solution validity to enable trustworthy onboard application.

DISCLAIMER

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Mand, D. Woffinden, P. Spanos, and R. Zanetti, “Rendezvous and Proximity Operations at the Earth-Moon L2 Lagrange Point: Navigation Analysis for Preliminary Trajectory Design,” *AAS/AIAA Astrodynamics Specialist Conference*, No. AAS 14-376, 2014.
- [2] G. Di Domenico, E. Andreis, A. C. Morelli, G. Merisio, V. Franzese, C. Giordano, A. Morselli, P. Panicucci, F. Ferrari, and F. Topputo, *The ERC-Funded EXTREMA Project: Achieving Self-Driving Interplanetary CubeSats*, pp. 167–199. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023, 10.1007/978-3-031-24812-2_6.
- [3] K. Oguri and J. W. McMahon, “Robust Spacecraft Guidance Around Small Bodies Under Uncertainty: Stochastic Optimal Control Approach,” *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, Vol. 44, No. 7, 2021, pp. 1295–1313, 10.2514/1.G005426.
- [4] A. W. Berning Jr., E. R. Burnett, and S. Bieniawski, “Chance-Constrained, Drift-Safe Guidance for Spacecraft Rendezvous,” *AAS Rocky Mountain Guidance, Navigation, and Control Conference*, American Astronautical Society, 2023, 10.48550/arXiv.2401.11077.
- [5] E. R. Burnett and F. Topputo, “A Monomial Method for Nonlinear Optimization in Astrodynamics,” *AAS Spaceflight Mechanics Meeting*, No. 25-218, American Astronautical Society, January 2025.
- [6] M. Berz, “Chapter 2 - Differential Algebraic Techniques,” *Modern Map Methods in Particle Beam Physics*, Vol. 108 of *Advances in Imaging and Electron Physics*, pp. 81–117, San Diego, CA: Academic Press, 1999, 10.1016/S1076-5670(08)70228-3.
- [7] Y. Mao, D. Dueri, M. Szmuk, and B. Açıkmeşe, “Successive Convexification of Non-Convex Optimal Control Problems with State Constraints,” *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, Vol. 50, No. 1, 2017, pp. 4063–4069. 20th IFAC World Congress, 10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.789.
- [8] H. Schaub and J. L. Junkins, *Analytical Mechanics of Space Systems*. Reston, VA: AIAA Education Series, 4th ed., 2018, 10.2514/4.105210.
- [9] G. Franzini and M. Innocenti, “Relative Motion Dynamics in the Restricted Three-Body Problem,” *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, Vol. 56, No. 5, 2019, pp. 1322–1337, 10.2514/1.A34390.
- [10] E. R. Burnett and F. Topputo, “Rapid nonlinear convex guidance using a monomial method,” arXiv preprint, 2024, 10.48550/arXiv.2403.19324.
- [11] A. Agrawal, R. Verschuere, S. Diamond, and S. Boyd, “A rewriting system for convex optimization problems,” *Journal of Control and Decision*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 2018, pp. 42–60, 10.1080/23307706.2017.1397554.
- [12] S. Diamond and S. Boyd, “CVXPY: A Python-embedded modeling language for convex optimization,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, Vol. 17, No. 83, 2016, pp. 1–5, 10.48550/arXiv.1603.00943.
- [13] M. Schaller, G. Banjac, S. Diamond, A. Agrawal, B. Stellato, and S. Boyd, “Embedded Code Generation With CVXPY,” *IEEE Control Systems Letters*, Vol. 6, 2022, pp. 2653–2658, 10.1109/LC-SYS.2022.3173209.
- [14] C. Peterson, R. J. Caverly, S. Phillips, and A. Weiss, “Safe and constrained rendezvous, proximity operations, and docking,” *American Control Conference (ACC)*, IEEE, Mar. 2023, pp. 3645–3661.